
Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

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ABSTRACT: This study focused on the perceived influence of micro-teaching skills on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education in Kwara State. The study answered two research questions and tested two null hypotheses in line with the stated objectives. The target population of the study comprised 904 NCE III (2021/2022) business education students in colleges of education (Private 126, State 461 and Federal 317) in Kwara State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 417 NCE III students from colleges of education in Ilorin. Data were collected using a modified student-teacher assessment form and a self-designed questionnaire titled "Perceived Influence of Micro-teaching Skills on - Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education (PIMSSPTCE)". Findings reveal that micro-teaching influences student-teacher communication skills and classroom management skills to a moderate extent. Based on the findings made, it is concluded that acquisition of relevant teaching skills is vital to teachers' preparation and training. Based on the conclusion drawn, it is recommended, among others, that the use of communication skills should be taught to student teachers in the NCE programme to enhance their performance during teaching practice.

KEYWORDS: Micro-teaching, Skills, Performance, Student-teacher, Teaching

1. INTRODUCTION

Micro-teaching is a scaled-down, simulated teaching encounter designed for the training of both pre-service and in-service teachers. According to Chuajin, Chummei, and Salawu (2011), micro-teaching has been in use worldwide since its invention at Stanford University in the late 1950s by Dwight, Robert, and Romney. Its purpose is to provide teachers with the opportunity for concept lessons in any teaching subject. Also, Hertel, Millis, Noyd, and Romesh (2013) described micro-teaching as a scaled-down, realistic classroom training context in which teachers, both experienced and inexperienced, may acquire new teaching skills and refine old ones. The micro-teaching environment enables a student teacher to focus attention on the practice of a specific skill at a time until he or she acquires competence in it. The provision of feedback accelerates this process. After acquiring competence in a number of skills in this way, the student teacher takes to microteaching in order to demonstrate his or her level of competence. Microteaching helps in overcoming such pitfalls. It provides a setting for experimentation. With the introduction of a developed curriculum, teachers are required to acquire new skills in teaching. The use of modern computers helps teachers in the preparation of lesson plans, keeping student records, accessing teaching resource materials, enhancing communication in education, and delivering lectures (Ojo, 2020).

From the experience of the researcher and, more importantly, from the researcher's contact with pre-service teachers (NCE and undergraduate), needed teaching skills are difficult to acquire, hence the need to integrate micro-teaching into the professional development of the pre-service teachers. Therefore, the researcher decided to dwell on some of the major skills of micro-teaching, which include classroom management skills and communication skills, among others. Experience has shown that, right from the introductory stage, a student teacher cannot demonstrate a sense of commitment in understanding the basic concept of micro-teaching as contained in the teacher training curriculum of colleges of education titled Micro Teaching Theory and coded EDU 213 offered at NCE level. Some candidates often choose teacher training institutions (the College of Education) as their last resort (JAMB, 2013). This might be connected with the attitude of the members of society toward teaching as a profession. The ability of the student teacher to transform an abstract idea into reality through the application of appropriate instructional materials is efficient.

Personal observation has shown that the microteaching skills as a fundamental principle of teaching are unsatisfactorily demonstrated by student teachers. This is seen in the weak application of the micro-teaching skill of chalkboard management by the student teacher, which makes the performance insufficient in the skill of clear writing, which leads to ineffectiveness in drawing the learners' attention. The weak use of the skill of reinforcement for encouraging positive responses by the student teacher during teaching and learning is not appropriate. The process of drawing the attention of the learner to concentrate on

Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

teaching and learning activities and to make the lesson more captivating via the skill of set-induction is completely discouraging. Ijaiya (2013) noted that many student-teachers fail to acquire sufficient teaching skills to the detriment of pupils' learning, and that when these skills are learned by the students during pre-service training, some of the student-teachers do not adequately apply their skills during teaching practice. Student teachers often go to the classroom without instructional materials; most of them fail to demonstrate communication skills and classroom management skills.

Similarly, Olaofe (2007) remarked that teacher quality has nosedived, resulting in a steady decline from the large number of teachers who could make pupils unlearn what they had accidentally learned elsewhere. In addition, there is a general decline in the number of professional teachers needed to teach in various institutions of learning in Nigeria. The aforementioned problems collectively constitute serious setbacks towards effective performance during the teaching and learning process, and eventually they could hinder the attainment of the designed instructional objectives during a teaching practice programme. These have manifested doubt in the mind of the researcher, especially in the efficiency of micro-teaching sessions in exposing student teachers undergoing teacher training programmes. These and many other similar issues have necessitated the need to embark on this research.

Statement of the Problem

Student-teachers are not performing optimally in teaching practice, probably due to the inadequacies of micro-teaching programs. From the researcher's experience, students' performance in teaching practice exercises has not been convincing enough to justify the efforts involved in Micro Teaching as courses. Micro-teaching involves so many skills, which, if harnessed effectively, should lead to successful performance in teaching practice. While in school, the student-teachers are exposed to micro-teaching skills during teaching practice.

To the best knowledge of the researcher, there is a dearth of studies focusing on the relationship between microteaching and teaching practice in colleges of education. This raises the question of whether microteaching adequately prepares students for teaching practice. The study, therefore, focused on the perceived influence of microteaching skills on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the Perceived Influence of Micro-teaching Skills on Student-teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education. The study will specifically examine:

1. the extent to which micro-teaching influences student-teachers' communication skill in Colleges of Education.
2. the extent to which micro-teaching influences student-teachers' classroom management skill in Colleges of Education.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does micro-teaching influences student-teachers' communication skill in Colleges of Education?
2. To what extent does micro-teaching influences student-teachers' classroom management skill in Colleges of Education?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: Communication skill does not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

H₀₂: Classroom management skill does not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

2. METHOD

The design of the study was correlation survey research. The population of the study was made up of 904 NCE III business education students from colleges of education in Ilorin metropolis of Kwara State (North Central), Nigeria who were posted to the field for teaching practice in 2022/2023. The sample size of 417 NCE III students (328 NCE III students of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin, and 89 NCE III students of Muhydeen College of Education, Ilorin) was selected using a simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were the Modified Student-Teacher Assessment Form (MSTAF), which was modified by the researcher from the original Micro-Teaching Practicum Assessment Guide (MITPAG) approved by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) to measure student teachers' performance in teaching practice, and a structured questionnaire tagged "PIMSSPTPCE". The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was validated and verified by experts in business education, measurements, and evaluation. The instrument had a reliability of 0.81. Percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions. Regression analysis was used to test

Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. If the observed significant value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance, the null hypotheses were rejected, and if otherwise, the null hypotheses were retained.

3. RESULTS

Research Question One: To what extent does micro-teaching influence student-teachers' communication skill in Colleges of Education?

Table 1: Mean responses on the influence of micro-teaching on student-teachers' communication skill

S/N	Item Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Enhances appropriate application of skill of communication in teaching and learning	3.28	0.69	Moderate Extent
2.	Enhances good summary of lesson	3.16	0.70	Moderate Extent
3.	Enhances writing clearly and boldly for the students	3.10	0.76	Moderate Extent
4.	Helps to communicate verbally/orally.	2.89	0.65	Moderate Extent
5.	Helps to write legibly on the board	3.53	0.57	High Extent
6.	Helps to communicate adequately in writing	3.37	0.59	Moderate Extent
7.	Enhances clarity of voice	3.23	0.64	Moderate Extent
8.	Helps to communicate adequately through nonverbal communication	2.75	0.70	Moderate Extent
9.	Enhances appropriate use of language and helps in student teacher's performance	3.23	0.73	Moderate Extent
Weighted average		3.17	0.67	Moderate Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 shows that the respondents agreed that micro-teaching enhances the appropriate application of the skill of communication in teaching and learning, provides a good summary of the lesson, and enhances the students' ability to write clearly and boldly. These were supported by mean scores of 3.28, 3.16, and 3.10, respectively. The respondents also agreed that microteaching helps students communicate verbally orally, write legibly on the board, and communicate adequately in writing. Mean scores of 2.89, 3.53, and 3.37 supported these. In addition, the respondents agreed that micro-teaching enhances clarity of voice, helps to communicate adequately through nonverbal communication, enhances appropriate use of language, and helps in the student-teacher's performance. These were supported by mean scores of 3.23, 2.75, and 3.23, respectively.

All the nine item constructs have standard deviations ranging from 0.57 to 0.76. This means that the responses of the respondents are not widely spread because they are close to the mean. Table 1 shows a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.17 and 0.67, which indicate that the respondents agreed to all the constructs to a moderate extent. This implies that micro-teaching has a moderate influence on student-teachers' communication skills in colleges of education (mean = 3.17, SD = 0.67).

Research Question Two: To what extent does micro-teaching experience influence student-teachers' classroom management skill in Colleges of Education?

Table 2: Mean responses on the influence of micro-teaching on student-teachers' classroom management skill

S/N	Item Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Helps the class environment to be very neat and tidy	3.18	0.67	Moderate Extent
2.	Helps to arrange the seating to allow for free and easy movement	3.01	0.66	Moderate Extent
3.	Helps to appoint/recognize a class leader who could pass relevant information to the class	3.19	0.67	Moderate Extent
4.	Helps to establish guiding principles of interaction in the class and to set up a channel of communication	3.03	0.67	Moderate Extent
5.	Helps to properly inform the class of new expectations	3.38	0.71	Moderate Extent
6.	Enhances Free flow of information when talking as to ensure every member of the class gets the required message	3.37	0.65	Moderate Extent
7.	Helps to reward those who deserve to be rewarded	3.17	0.72	Moderate Extent
8.	Helps to caution/discipline those who deserve to be disciplined	3.10	0.74	Moderate Extent
9.	Enhances discipline and orderliness in the classroom	3.21	0.74	Moderate Extent
10.	Helps to spot some students that are unprepared for their lesson	3.18	0.67	Moderate Extent
Weighted average		3.18	0.69	Moderate Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows that the respondents agreed that micro-teaching helps the class environment to be very neat and tidy, helps to arrange the seating to allow for free and easy movement, and helps to appoint or recognize a class leader who could pass relevant

Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

information to the class. These are supported by mean scores of 3.18, 3.01, and 3.19, respectively. The respondents also agreed that micro-teaching helps to establish guiding principles of interaction in the class, set up a channel of communication, properly inform the class of new expectations, and enhance the free flow of information when talking so that every member of the class gets the required message. Mean scores of 3.03, 3.38, and 3.37 supported these. In addition, the respondents agreed that microteaching helps to reward those who deserve to be rewarded, caution or discipline those who deserve to be disciplined, enhances discipline and orderliness in the classroom, and helps to spot some students that are unprepared for their lesson. These were supported by mean scores of 3.17, 3.10, 3.21, and 3.18, respectively.

All the ten item constructs have a standard deviation range of 0.65 to 0.74. This means that the responses of the respondents are not widely spread because they are close to the mean. Table 2 shows a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.18 and 0.69, which indicate that the respondents agreed to all the constructs to a moderate extent. This implies that micro-teaching has a moderate influence on student-teachers' classroom management skills in colleges of education (mean = 3.18, SD = 0.69).

Hypotheses Testing

Four null hypotheses are tested using linear regression at 0.05 level of significance. The summary of the test of hypotheses are presented in Tables 8 to 15 as follows:

H₀₁: Communication skill does not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Analysis on the influence of communication skill on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-cal.	P-value
1	417	0.076	0.006	0.003	2.395	0.023

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Communication skill

Table 4: Test of significance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	55.136	4.288		12.858	0.000	46.707	63.565
Communication Skill	2.085	1.347	0.076	1.548	0.023	0.563	4.733

Dependent Variable: Communication skill

Table 3 summarises the regression analysis results of the influence of communication skills on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education. The result indicates that there is a positive relationship between communication skill and student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($R = 0.076$), while R-squared is 0.006, which means that the independent variable (communication skill) explains 0.06% variations of the dependent variable (students' performance).

The test of significance results as presented in Table 4 show that communication skills significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($B = 2.085$; $t_{(416)} = 1.548$, $P = 0.023$). It indicates that at the 5% level of significance, there is enough evidence that the regression equation specifies that communication skills significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that communication skill significantly influences student-teacher performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

H₀₂: Classroom management skill does not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

Table 5: Summary of Regression Analysis on influence of classroom management skill on student-teachers' performance in teaching practice

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-cal.	P-value
1	417	.078	.006	.004	2.517	.013

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Classroom management skill

Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

Table 6: Test of significance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95% Confidence Interval		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	52.322	5.953		8.790	.000	40.621	64.023
Classroom Management Skill	2.961	1.866	0.078	1.586	.013	0.708	6.629

Dependent Variable: Classroom management skill

Table 5 summarises the regression analysis results of the influence of classroom management skills on students' and teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education. The result indicates that there is a positive relationship between classroom management skill and student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($R = 0.078$), while R-squared is 0.006, which means that the independent variable (classroom management skill) explained 0.06% variations of the dependent variable (students' performance).

The test of significance results as presented in Table 6 show that classroom management skills significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($B = 2.961$; $t_{(416)} = 1.586$; $P = 0.013$). It indicates that at the 5% level of significance, there is enough evidence that the regression equation specifies that classroom management skill significantly influences student-teachers' performance in teaching practice. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that classroom management skill significantly influences student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education.

4. DISCUSSION

Findings on research question one revealed that communication skills acquired during micro-teaching significantly and positively influence student-teachers' performance to a moderate extent. This implies that it enhances appropriate application of communication skills in teaching and learning, enhances writing clearly and boldly for the students, enhances appropriate use of language, and helps in the student teacher's performance. In addition, findings on hypothesis one revealed that there was a positive relationship between communication skill and student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($B = 2.085$; $t_{(416)} = 1.548$, $P = 0.023$). Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that communication skills did not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education, was rejected. This implies that communication skill significantly influences student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education in Kwara State. This finding agrees with that of Bashir (2009) and Ismail (2011) that microteaching skill has significant influence on student-teachers' effectiveness in teaching practice. This finding also correlates with those of Dagnev (2011), who revealed that micro-teaching programmes provide the student-teachers with positive impacts on communication skills and the use of teaching materials needed during teaching practice.

Findings on research question two showed that classroom management skills acquired during microteaching significantly and positively influence student-teachers' performance to a moderate extent. This indicates that it helps to arrange the seating to allow for free and easy movement, helps to establish guiding principles of interaction in the class and to set up a channel of communication, and enhances the free flow of information when talking so that every member of the class gets the required message. In addition, findings on hypothesis two revealed that classroom management skills significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice ($B = 2.961$; $t_{(416)} = 1.586$, $P = 0.013$). Thus, the null hypotheses, which stated that classroom management skill does not significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education, were rejected. This implies that classroom management skills significantly influence student-teachers' performance in teaching practice in colleges of education in Kwara State. This finding is similar to that of Abdulrahman (2010), which reveals that micro-teaching provides the student teacher with the knowledge of how to use the skill of classroom management as it modifies their behaviour toward planning the teaching process, classroom control, communication, and evaluation.

5. CONCLUSION

Finding from this study revealed that micro-teaching experiences have effect on teaching practice performance of student-teachers in colleges of education in Kwara State. Since teaching practice enables prospective teachers to get their first teaching experience, which they find valuable during their professional life, the learning of relevant teaching skills is essential to teachers' preparation and training. The usage of micro-teaching skills in a teaching practice session also lowers students' anxiety levels and offers them the chance to organise their classes and use new teaching and learning skills.

Perceived Influence of Micro-Teaching Skills on Student-Teachers' Performance in Teaching Practice in Colleges of Education in Kwara State

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Student-teachers should put their communication skills into practice during the microteaching period and keep working at it until they are fully proficient at all facets of communication.
2. Teacher educators should make a greater effort to ensure that student teachers understand and apply the skill of classroom management to improve performance both during and after teaching practice.

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